

PERINATAL LESIONS OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

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The word perinatal itself suggests that perinatal CNS damage develops in an unborn or newborn baby.

Perinatal damage of the central nervous system (PPCNS) is not one, but several diagnoses that involve dysfunction in the brain of a newborn child and can lead to persistent neurological consequences at an older age (e.g. cerebral palsy, cerebral palsy).

The entire perinatal period is conventionally divided into three stages:

- The antenatal period lasts from 28 weeks until the time of delivery;
- the birth process itself is called the intrapartum period;
- The neonatal period is the time interval from the moment of birth up to and including the 7th day of life.

In modern medicine, there is no exact name for the disease when the fetal CNS is affected, there is only a compilation, it is called PPCNS or perinatal encephalopathy. Perinatal affection of the central nervous system in newborns is manifested by disorders of the motor apparatus, speech and mental disorders.

With the development of medicine, this diagnosis is no longer used for children older than one month. After one month, the doctor must make an accurate diagnosis of the child. It is during this period that the neurologist accurately determines how badly the nervous system is damaged. He prescribes treatment and makes sure it is chosen correctly.

What are the causes and risk factors for PPCNS?

The reasons why perinatal damage to the central nervous system can develop are quite varied, among the most popular are:

- Maternal somatic disease, which is accompanied by chronic intoxication;
- the presence of acute infectious diseases or chronic foci of infection, while the expectant mother carried the child;
- if the woman has an impaired nutritional process, or if she is not mature enough for pregnancy and childbirth;
- disruption of uterine and placental blood flow during pregnancy;
- Changes in metabolism also cause nervous system disorders in the unborn child (elevated bilirubin levels, neonatal jaundice);
- in the case of severe toxicity, both early and late, or the emergence of other problems with carrying a child;
- The environment is an important factor in the development of the disease;

- The emergence of pathology during childbirth - it may be a weak labor, accelerated delivery;
- If the baby is born prematurely, then his body is not fully developed, so against this background, there may be a violation of the CNS;
- Babies with hereditary factors are at the highest risk of developing CNS lesions. All the other causes of PPCNS are situational, and it is simply impossible to predict their occurrence.

There are several pathways for the development of perinatal CNS lesions in newborn children depending on the cause and subsequent symptomatology, analysis of which allows the initial diagnosis to be made.